

"A Study of Men-Women Relationship in Doris Lessing's Novel: *The Golden Notebook*"

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Abstract

Doris Lessing's women characters are always bound within masculine sexuality and they define themselves through their relationship with men. This research article will show that being far from celebrating women's independence from men, the novel *The Golden Notebook* (1962) explores the complementary relationship between men and women, and the inescapable need for the opposite sex. This article will try to focus on such areas as: even if a woman is free of marriage, she is still bound to her biological nature and drives. It is not explicitly a feminine text and it does not endorse arguments about sexual difference or call for sexual isolationism.

Keywords: masculine, sexuality, complementary, biological, feminine, explicitly.

Introduction

Doris Lessing's novel *The Golden Notebook* (1962) is her remarkable work and considered as the Bible of Women's Movement of the late 1960s. It is seen as a pioneering work and is counted among a handful of books that brought to light the relationship between male and female of the twentieth century. The novel focuses on Anna Wulf, the main character and her notebooks; therein her thoughts about Africa, politics, the Communist party, her relationship with men and sex are candidly dealt. The psyche of the characters are reflected in a disjointed form. Anna, being a writer, was caught in a personal and artistic crisis, who observes her life as being compartmentalised into various roles as a woman, lover, writer, political activist. Her diaries, written in different coloured notebooks each corresponding to a different part of herself.

She eventually suffers a mental breakdown and it is only through this disintegration that she is able to discover a new "wholeness" which she writes about in the final book i.e. *The Golden Notebook*.

Doris Lessing has disclaimed in her 1971 Preface to *The Golden Notebook* that the novel is not a flag-bearer of the Women's Liberation Movement. But it certainly does raise questions about women as stereotypes in a patriarchal society and their subordination to men. Lessing's women characters---Anna and Molly, Ella and Julia---strongly resent the sexist assumption of men that they are either sex-hungry or under-miners and sappers. They resist men's attempts to infringe their liberty and pigeonhole them. *The Golden Notebook* goes a long way to dismantle the received notions of gender-speak. Anna and Molly are as free as men in all the major areas of life: politics, sex, profession and writing. They are also more intelligent and responsive than their lovers who are quite often found to be either sexual cripples or disoriented dreamers. But the question arises: are they really "free"?

Complex Men-Women Relationships

On closer scrutiny, one would find that far from celebrating women's freedom from men, *The Golden Notebook* explores the complex relationships between men and women, and stresses the unavoidable need for the opposite sex. The protagonist Anna's identity is based on love and dependency and she finds happiness in the company of the man she loves:

The truth is I don't care a damn about politics or philosophy or anything else, all I care about is that Michael should turn in the dark and put his face against my breasts. (The Golden Notebook, P.219)

Anna always defines herself through her relationship with men. The relationships portrayed in the novel are usually troubled and fraught with tension and hostility, invariably ending in an emotional fiasco. But running throughout the novel is the implicit sub-text---the evocative idea of a woman wanting to live happily with her lover, to shop, cook and wait for him, to be emotionally and sexually fulfilled by him. Heterosexual relationships are central to the overall meaning of the book. Lessing's women characters are always bound within male sexuality and they define themselves through their relationships with men.

Time and again, Anna and her character/alter-ego Ella express unfeministic needs and sentiments. At one point in the yellow notebook, Ella says:

Women's emotions are still fitted for a kind of society that no longer exists. My deep emotions, my real ones, are to do with my relationships with a man. One man. But I don't live that kind of life, and I know few women who do.(The Golden Notebook, P.229)

Anna worries in the beginning about inviting "defeat from men" or being fast in an emotion common to women of our time, that can turn them bitter, or lesbian or solitary". But she confesses at the end that her "strongest need" is "being with one man, love, and all that I've a real talent for it." She realizes that women's "real loyalties are always to men, and not to women".

She is highly critical of women's naiveté, failure to learn from mistakes and their "capacity for not thinking" when they reach out for happiness.

Search for a "Real Man"

Along with women's hopeless dependence on men, *The Golden Notebook* also demonstrates the shattering effect of being abandoned by men. When Michael leaves Anna for another woman after five years of living together, she feels completely disintegrated and suffers from pangs of severe loneliness, depression and sterility. And Paul's desertion of Ella, at a time when she has started depending on him, leaves her disoriented and listless, "as if (he) had taken with him not only her capacity for joy, but also her will". She suffers from "torments of sexual desire" and understands that "she is dependent on men, for 'having sex', for 'being serviced', for 'being satisfied'." Ella hopes that she will become normal when she falls in love with a man again because a "woman's sexuality is ... contained by a man, if he is a real man".

The search for a "real man" or right man, one who will fulfil a woman emotionally and sexually and help her find herself, is a major preoccupation of Lessing's female characters. They are ready to compromise and sacrifice, even overlook their lovers' infidelities, for the sake of a durable relationship. In the yellow notebook Ella says:

Suppose Paul had said to me: I'll marry you if you promise never to write another word? My God, I would have done it! . (The Golden Notebook, P.311)

The novel does not advocate sexual revolution and autonomy for women but lays stress on normal, healthy men-women relationships based on mutual love and respect. As Lessing herself has remarked. "I'm impatient with people who emphasise sexual revolution. I say we should all go to bed, shut up about sexual liberation, and go on with important matters."

Empowerment of Males

It is true that the men who come into Anna's life-Michael, Nelson, De Silva, Saul Green-invariably fail her. They prove themselves to be selfish, opportunistic and even exploitative. Through her sexual involvement with them she learns that men can be cruel, hurtful and destructive of women but one cannot do without them. She, therefore, reconciles herself to being a "boulder-pusher", a latter-day Sisyphus pushing a huge rock up the black mountain of human stupidity in the hope that sooner or later her effort will be shared by some mature men. Hence, even when her lovers are found to be bad and devitalised, Anna does not discard them. She encourages the men and tries to bolster them up.

Empowerment of males is a recurring motif in *The Golden Notebook*. At one point in her diary, Anna writes:

I am always amazed, in myself and in other women, at the strength of our need to bolster men up. This is ironical, living as we do in a time of men's criticizing us for being "castrating" ... for the truth is, women have this deep instinctive need to build a man up

as a man... I suppose this is because real men become fewer and fewer, and we are frightened, trying to create men. (The Golden Notebook, P.356)

It is not at all a coincidence that Anna's writing "block" is lifted by a male who is equally helped by her. Lessing's "free women" want to redeem their men so that they can lead a healthy and peaceful life, and work together to liberate the world from ignorance, oppression, tyranny and exploitation. She does not endorse any argument about sexual difference or call for sexual separatism.

Conclusion

The Golden Notebook, a consciousness-raising novel, makes a strong plea against artificial splits or divisions. Its final message is not fragmentation but unity and cohesion. Despite her profound sympathy for women's problems, Lessing is not reductive in her approach to, and assessment of, the human predicament. Robert Rubenstein aptly remarks: "Ultimately, the deepest task of (Lessing's) characters is to achieve a personal wholeness that subsumes sexual identity or gender under a larger principle of growth. The challenge to the protagonists... is in the enlargement of the human spirit that is shared equally by both sexes without denying the importance of their progress or development of awareness as women ... an identification that goes beyond their sexual identities. The body may be enclosed by biology but the mind is not."

References

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